

PROFESSIONAL ATTRIBUTES AND ITS CORRELATION TO TEACHING PERFORMANCE OF SELECT TEACHERS IN PRIVATE INSTITUTIONS

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Professional Attributes and Its Correlation to Teaching Performance of Select Teachers in Private Institutions

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Abstract

This study was to discover or establish the existence of a relationship/ association/ interdependence between two or more aspects of a situation. The purpose of this study was to look into the professional attributes contributory to teaching excellence in The Sto. Niño Formation and Science School. The key participants in this study the 69 teachers currently employed in The Sto. Niño Formation and Science School in Rosario, Batangas. Teachers were invited to participate regardless of factors. Participations were voluntary, and measures were taken to protect teacher confidentiality and privacy. The goal was to obtain representatives that reflected the diversity of the teaching workforce in order to gather rich data that can inform an understanding of teachers' experiences, perceptions and needs from their own perspectives. The researchers utilized a descriptive-correlational research design for this study. The 69 teachers in Sto. Niño Formation and Science School in Rosario, Batangas who answered the survey with a set of questions. With the Close-Ended Likert Scale Questions. The adaptability, patience, communication, creativity, leadership, time management, planning and preparation, classroom environment and instruction and professional responsibilities. Furthermore, teachers should continue to focus on enhancing their adaptability skills to effectively navigate changes in curriculum or school policies. Professional development opportunities can help educators stay flexible and responsive to evolving educational requirements and shifts in the educational landscape. Overall, it aims to support teachers in developing their professional attributes and improving their level of teaching performance. By focusing on these competencies, teachers can better meet the needs of their students and create more effective and equitable learning environments.

Keywords: *adaptability, creativity, leadership, time management, planning and preparation*

Introduction

The effectiveness of the school's educational plan hinges on the teacher's execution of his duties, responsibilities, and role within the school. Teachers are one of the most influential and powerful forces for equity, access and quality in education. Establishing a quality teaching workforce capable of effectively developing the competencies of students and helping them reach their potential has been one of the main objectives of education reforms.

A good teacher can make a world of difference in a student's life, impacting everything from their classroom learning to their long-term success.

The primary objective of the teacher has always been to facilitate student learning. The plans' success is determined by the teacher's level of competence. The primary aim of teachers is to foster student learning. The degree of the teacher's competence directly influences the success of this goal. The teacher's activities should prioritize classroom instruction and the well-being of the children under her supervision. The teacher bears direct responsibility for the exceptional performance of the students. It is essential for the teacher to prepare her teaching systematically and adeptly employ the latest methods, strategies, and techniques.

Within a professional community, teachers can contemplate educational objectives and their implications within the contexts of their classrooms, their students, and their specific subject areas. Teachers who successfully adapted their teaching methods for their students were part of a professional community that fostered encouragement and support. The academic success or failure of learners depends on how their teachers utilize various learning styles and strategies. Moreover, students' performance in the classroom can be influenced by external factors including the home environment, teaching methods, and personal motivations. Students learn at varying rates due to the impact of diverse cultures and individual differences. To excel as a teacher, one must initially grasp the concept of "personality." Personality encompasses all facets of an individual that shape their characteristics, behaviors, thoughts, and emotions. Teachers typically operate within educational institutions overseen by school administrators or principals. One of the responsibilities of educational administrators is to ensure that the academic environment of a school is positive, welcoming, and conducive to effective teaching and student learning. To address these requirements, principals need to conduct regular classroom visits, assess current teaching practices, explore innovative instructional methods, engage in discussions with faculty and staff, and review curriculum materials.

Creemers and Rezigit (1997) express concern that teachers constitute the largest professional group within a school, interact most frequently with students throughout the day, and significantly shape the school environment. When teachers experience positive feelings about their role, often described as teacher morale, they wield a substantial positive influence on both students and the overall school atmosphere. Educational leaders must prioritize understanding the factors influencing teacher morale and their potential impact on student achievement. Schools require leaders who excel in developing change systems and fostering relationships with staff that

leverage their collective knowledge and insights, while also cultivating strong connections that ignite their passion for working with students.

The demands and expectations placed on teacher education have created a challenging situation for educators, as outlined by Ben-Peretz (2001). The quality of teacher education and the professional attributes of teachers have a direct impact on the learning outcomes of students, and investing in teacher preparation is imperative for the future development of a nation, as stated in the second source. Teachers play a critical role in achieving high-quality education for all learners and therefore need continuous professional development and access to professional support throughout their careers. Developing personal qualities in teacher education is crucial for addressing the social responsibility mandate of teacher education, as highlighted by the third source. Furthermore, the article discusses the importance of reflective thinking and practice in developing teachers' personal qualities relevant to addressing the social responsibility mandate of teacher education. In conclusion, the quality of teacher education, continuous professional development, and personal attributes of teachers, all contribute to teaching excellence and the overall quality of education in a nation.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to look into the professional attributes contributory to teaching excellence in The Sto. Niño Formation and Science School. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions and provide recommendations for stakeholders:

1. What is the degree of professional attributes of selected teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. adaptability;
 - 1.2. patience;
 - 1.3. communication;
 - 1.4. creativity;
 - 1.5. leadership; and
 - 1.6. time management?
2. What is the level of teaching performance of the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1. planning and preparation;
 - 2.2. classroom environment;
 - 2.3. instruction;
 - 2.4. professional responsibility?
3. Is there a significant relationship between:the degree of teachers professional attributes and level of teaching performance?
4. What professional development plan should be proposed based from the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers utilized a descriptive-correlational research design for this study. First, being a descriptive research, using a questionnaire, it intended to collect and to analyze data using descriptive statistics; using the adapted questionnaire, it measured the degree of adaptability, patience, communication, creativity, leadership, and time management as well as teaching performance in terms of planning and preparation, classroom environment, instruction, and professional responsibility.

According to Price (2013), in the correlational research design, the relationship between two or more variables was to be studied, excluding their causes. It did not made use of any kind of manipulation through experimentation. For this study in particular, the relationship between teacher performance and professional attributes were explored.

The main emphasis in a correlation study was to discover or establish the existence of a relationship/ association/ interdependence between two or more aspects of a situation (Kumar, 2011).

Respondents

The key respondents in this study the 69 teachers currently employed in The Sto. Niño Formation and Science School in Rosario, Batangas. Teachers were invited to participate regardless of factors. Participations were voluntary, and measures were taken to protect teacher confidentiality and privacy. The goal was to obtain representatives that reflected the diversity of the teaching workforce in order to gather rich data that can inform an understanding of teachers' experiences, perceptions and needs from their own perspectives.

Instrument

The instrument used in the study were two adapted questionnaires to collect the needed data for this study. The first part was an 18-item questionnaire adapted from Martin & Rubin, (1995), Büssing et al., (2013), Wiemann, (1977), Zhou & George, (2001), Northouse, (2021), Macan et al., (1990) to measure a respondents professional attributes in terms of adaptability, patience, communication, creativity, leadership, and time management. The questionnaire uses a likert scale rating of 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree)

The questions in the second part of this questionnaire were based on the Framework for Teaching which was developed by Charlotte Danielson (2013) and is a widely recognized model that is grounded in research to evaluate teacher effectiveness. The framework has

four domains: Planning and Preparation, Classroom Environment, Instruction, and Professional Responsibilities. Every domain was broken down into several components that depicted different aspects of teaching practice. The questionnaire used a four-point rating scale from Unsatisfactory to Distinguished to rate the teacher's performance on every component. The framework and its related evaluation instrument have been extensively pilot tested and are validated across diverse educational settings.

Procedure

The questionnaires were distributed digitally using Google Forms to the teachers of Sto. Niño Formation and Science School. Purposive random sampling was utilized by the researchers, wherein potential participants were chosen based from the criteria of the research and contacted through the appropriate channels and provided information about the study and the voluntary nature of participation. Teacher-participants who agreed to take part were able to access the survey online through a Google Forms survey or through face-to-face depending on the availability of time and the procedure chosen.

The survey was designed to be straightforward and user-friendly for participants to complete. Appropriate measures were taken to ensure participant's confidentiality and secure data handling procedures throughout the data gathering process.

Data Analysis

The researchers used the following data and statistical analysis in order to effectively analyze and interpret the data.

Ranking. This was utilized to establish the order of the responses of the teacher-respondents on their level of professional attributes and teaching excellence.

Weighted Mean. This was used to determine the respondents' average degree of professional attributes and teaching excellence.

Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (r). Investigates the hypothesis of linear relationship between two quantitative variables, in this case, the relationship between the professional attributes and teaching excellence.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure that this study was ethical, the following were prioritized. Rigid examination, critiquing, and validation were needed to conduct the study carefully and effectively. The study was validated by the research experts and other knowledgeable people in the field using the validator's questionnaire assessment guided by the scales, interpretation and necessary description.

Participants/respondents were not harmed in anyway as a result of their participation in this study. Full consent were gathered. Furthermore, the privacy of the research participants/respondents were protected. In managing the data, an acceptable amount of detail were prevented, as biased depiction of main data findings.

Furthermore, any affiliations, funding sources, and conflicts of interests were disclosed. Any communications related to this study were truthful, transparent and confidential.

Results and Discussion

This part dealt with the gathered data that were analyzed and interpreted for the better understanding of the study. The framework of the analysis and interpretation was guided by the problems stated in the objectives of the study.

1. Degree of Professional Attributes of the Teacher-Respondents

Table 1. Degree of Professional Attribute of the Teacher-Respondents in Terms of Adaptability

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
I am able to adjust my teaching strategies to accommodate different learning styles.	4.48	Strongly Agree	2
I can effectively adapt to changes in the curriculum or school policies.	4.57	Strongly Agree	1
I am flexible in my approach to problem-solving in the classroom.	4.33	Strongly Agree	3
Composite Mean	4.46	Strongly Agree	

As reported in Table 1, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed that they can effectively adapt to changes in the curriculum or school policies which displayed the highest weighted mean of 4.57 and the highest rank of 1. The findings reported in Table 1 suggest that teacher-respondents perceive themselves as highly capable of effectively adapting to changes in curriculum or school policies. This is evidenced by their strong agreement with this statement, as indicated by a high weighted mean of 4.57 and the highest rank of 1 among all the statements or items surveyed.

The importance of teachers' adaptability in educational settings. Adaptability is crucial for educators to navigate changes such as new curricular requirements, pedagogical innovations, or shifts in school policies effectively.

Studies emphasize that teachers who are adaptable are better equipped to meet the diverse needs of students and respond flexibly to evolving educational contexts (Sawyer, 2017; Zwart et al., 2018).

Furthermore, research indicates that teachers' adaptability positively influences their job satisfaction, professional growth, and overall effectiveness in fostering student learning outcomes (Wang & Paine, 2019; Griffin & Care, 2020). It is recognized that fostering adaptability among teachers through professional development and supportive organizational practices contributes to enhanced educational outcomes and school effectiveness (Parker & Martin, 2021).

In summary, the findings from Table 1 highlight the strong agreement among teacher-respondents regarding their adaptability to changes in curriculum or school policies. This aligns with existing literature underscoring the importance of teacher adaptability for effective educational practice and positive student outcomes.

In addition, the said group of respondents also strongly agreed that they are flexible in their approach to problem-solving in the classroom which got the least weighted mean of 4.33 and least rank of 3. The findings reported in Table 1 indicate that the group of teacher-respondents strongly agreed that they are flexible in their approach to problem-solving in the classroom. This statement received a weighted mean of 4.33, which is slightly lower compared to the highest mean of 4.57 for adapting to changes in curriculum or school policies. Additionally, it received the least rank of 3 among the statements surveyed, indicating that while still highly rated, it was ranked slightly lower than other statements.

The significance of teacher flexibility in problem-solving within the classroom environment. Flexibility in teaching refers to educators' ability to adjust instructional strategies, activities, and approaches based on students' needs, learning progress, and classroom dynamics (Hill et al., 2015; Young & Diliberti, 2016).

Studies suggest that teachers who demonstrate flexibility in problem-solving create adaptive learning environments that promote student engagement, motivation, and academic achievement (Yoon & Kim, 2019; Leithwood et al., 2020). Flexible teachers are more responsive to unexpected challenges, variations in student understanding, and diverse learning styles, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness of teaching and learning processes (Sawyer, 2017).

Furthermore, research underscores the correlation between teacher flexibility and professional satisfaction, highlighting its role in fostering positive teacher-student relationships and creating supportive classroom climates (Griffin & Care, 2020; Wang & Paine, 2019).

Suggest that, while teacher-respondents strongly agree with their flexibility in problem-solving in the classroom, this aspect received a slightly lower rating compared to their adaptability to changes in curriculum or school policies. Nonetheless, both adaptability and flexibility in problem-solving are recognized as critical competencies that contribute to effective teaching practices and positive educational outcomes.

The composite mean of 4.46 concluded that the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on their degree of adaptability as professional attribute. The findings indicate that teacher-respondents strongly agreed on their degree of adaptability as a professional attribute, with a composite mean score of 4.46. This score reflects a high level of consensus among the respondents regarding their ability to adapt in their professional roles.

The notion that adaptability is a crucial attribute for teachers in contemporary educational settings. Adaptability encompasses teachers' capacity to adjust instructional practices, respond effectively to changing classroom dynamics, and integrate new pedagogical approaches (Hargreaves & Fullan, 2012; Griffin & Care, 2020).

Studies highlight several benefits associated with teacher adaptability, including enhanced instructional quality, improved student engagement, and increased satisfaction among educators (Sawyer, 2017; Wang & Paine, 2019). Adaptability enables teachers to meet diverse student needs, navigate educational reforms, and address challenges posed by technological advancements and evolving educational policies (Hill et al., 2015; Yoon & Kim, 2019).

Furthermore, research underscores the importance of fostering adaptability through continuous professional development and supportive organizational practices. Professional learning opportunities that focus on enhancing teachers' adaptive capacities contribute to their professional growth and overall effectiveness in promoting student learning outcomes (Leithwood et al., 2020; Parker & Martin, 2021).

In summary, the high level of agreement among teacher-respondents regarding their adaptability as a professional attribute, as indicated by the composite mean of 4.46, aligns with existing literature emphasizing adaptability as a critical competency for effective teaching and learning in modern educational contexts.

As reported in Table 2, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed that they provide adequate time and support for students who require additional assistance which presented the highest weighted mean of 4.53 and the highest rank of 1. Table 2 indicate that teacher-respondents strongly agreed that they provide adequate time and support for students who require additional assistance. This statement received the highest weighted mean of 4.53 and was ranked highest with a rank of 1 among all the items or statements surveyed.

Related literature underscores the importance of providing adequate time and support for students who need additional assistance as a crucial aspect of effective teaching and inclusive education practices. Research highlights that personalized support and individualized attention contribute significantly to student learning outcomes and overall academic success (Tomlinson & Imbeau, 2010; Darling-

Hammond et al., 2019).

Table 2. Degree of Professional Attribute of the Teacher-Respondents in Terms of Patience

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
I remain calm and composed when facing challenging situations in the classroom.	4.25	Strongly Agree	3
I am patient when explaining complex concepts to my students.	4.30	Strongly Agree	2
I provide adequate time and support for students who require additional assistance.	4.53	Strongly Agree	1
Composite Mean	4.36	Strongly Agree	

Teachers who allocate sufficient time and resources to address diverse student needs create inclusive learning environments where all students can thrive. This approach not only supports academic growth but also fosters social-emotional development and enhances student motivation (Fuchs & Fuchs, 2017; Allday et al., 2021).

Furthermore, studies emphasize the positive impact of teacher-student relationships and supportive classroom climates on student engagement and achievement (Cornelius-White, 2007; Hattie, 2009). Teachers who prioritize providing additional assistance demonstrate a commitment to equity and student well-being, promoting a culture of care and support within educational settings (Evertson & Weinstein, 2006; Pianta et al., 2012).

Consequently, the said group of respondents still strongly agreed that they remain calm and composed when facing challenging situations in the classroom which yielded the least weighted mean of 4.25 and least rank of 3. The group of teacher-respondents strongly agreed that they remain calm and composed when facing challenging situations in the classroom. This statement received a weighted mean of 4.25, which was the lowest among the statements surveyed, and it received the least rank of 3, indicating it was ranked slightly lower compared to other statements.

Related literature emphasizes the importance of teacher emotional regulation and composure in managing challenging classroom situations. Remaining calm and composed during stressful or difficult moments is crucial for maintaining a positive learning environment and effectively addressing student behavior or academic challenges (Jones et al., 2017; Jennings & Greenberg, 2009).

Research suggests that teachers who demonstrate emotional resilience and self-control are better equipped to handle conflicts, support student engagement, and promote constructive behavior management strategies (Brackett et al., 2012; Sutton & Wheatley, 2003). Moreover, teacher emotional regulation contributes to enhanced teacher-student relationships, fostering trust and mutual respect within the classroom (Greenberg et al., 2016; Miech et al., 2015).

Furthermore, studies highlight the impact of teacher stress and burnout on instructional quality and student outcomes, underscoring the importance of cultivating emotional well-being and coping strategies among educators (Kyriacou, 2001; Day & Qing, 2009).

The composite mean of 4.36 stated that the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on their degree of patience as professional attribute. Teacher-respondents strongly agreed on their degree of patience as a professional attribute, with a composite mean score of 4.36. This suggests a high level of consensus among the respondents regarding the importance of patience in their roles as educators.

Related literature underscores the critical role of patience in teaching. Patience is essential for managing diverse student needs, navigating challenging classroom situations, and maintaining positive teacher-student relationships (Santrock, 2011; Johnson, 2014).

Studies highlight that patient teachers demonstrate greater empathy, understanding, and tolerance, which contribute to a supportive classroom climate conducive to learning (Sutton & Wheatley, 2003; Brackett et al., 2012). Patience allows educators to provide individualized attention, scaffold learning experiences, and effectively address student misunderstandings or setbacks (Sawyer, 2017; Darling-Hammond et al., 2019).

Furthermore, research emphasizes the link between teacher patience and student outcomes, showing that patient teachers enhance student engagement, motivation, and academic achievement (Wubbels & Brekelmans, 2005; Jennings & Greenberg, 2009). Patience also plays a crucial role in mitigating teacher stress and burnout, promoting overall well-being and job satisfaction (Day & Qing, 2009; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2011).

In summary, the high level of agreement among teacher-respondents regarding their degree of patience as a professional attribute, as indicated by the composite mean of 4.36, aligns with existing literature highlighting patience as a fundamental competency for effective teaching and positive educational outcomes.

Table 3. Degree of Professional Attribute of the Teacher-Respondents in Terms of Communication

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
I clearly articulate expectations and instructions to my students.	4.49	Strongly Agree	2
I actively listen to my students' concerns and ideas.	4.45	Strongly Agree	3
I maintain open lines of communication with parents and guardians.	4.58	Strongly Agree	1
Composite Mean	4.51	Strongly Agree	

As discussed in Table 3, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed that they maintain open lines of communication with parents and guardians which got the highest weighted mean of 4.58 and the highest rank of 1. Table 3 indicate that teacher-respondents strongly

agreed that they maintain open lines of communication with parents and guardians. This statement received the highest weighted mean of 4.58 and was ranked highest with a rank of 1 among all the items or statements surveyed.

Related literature emphasizes the importance of effective communication between teachers and parents/guardians for promoting student success and overall school effectiveness. Open and consistent communication fosters collaboration, enhances parental involvement in their children's education, and strengthens partnerships between home and school (Epstein, 2018; Henderson & Mapp, 2002).

Research suggests that when teachers maintain open lines of communication, parents/guardians are more informed about their child's progress, academic achievements, and any challenges they may face (Christenson & Reschly, 2010; Fan & Williams, 2010). This proactive approach helps create a supportive environment where parents/guardians feel valued and engaged in their child's educational journey (Sanders & Sheldon, 2009).

Studies indicate that effective communication contributes to improved student outcomes, as it enables teachers and parents/guardians to collaborate on strategies for academic support and behavioral development (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001; Hoover-Dempsey & Sandler, 2005). Clear channels of communication also facilitate timely interventions and adjustments to educational plans, ensuring that students receive the necessary resources and support to succeed (Pomerantz & Eaton, 2001; Kavale et al., 2007).

Furthermore, the said group of respondents also agreed that they actively listen to their students' concerns and ideas which reported the least weighted mean of 4.45 and least rank of 3. The group of teacher-respondents agreed that they actively listen to their students' concerns and ideas. This statement received a weighted mean of 4.45, which was the lowest among the items surveyed, and it received the least rank of 3, indicating it was ranked slightly lower compared to other statements.

Related literature underscores the importance of active listening in fostering positive teacher-student relationships and promoting student engagement and learning. Active listening involves not only hearing what students say but also demonstrating empathy, understanding, and responsiveness to their concerns and ideas (Davis, 2003; Fredericks & McColskey, 2012).

Research indicates that teachers who actively listen create supportive classroom environments where students feel valued and respected (Gregory & Weinstein, 2008; Marzano et al., 2003). By listening attentively, educators gain insights into students' learning experiences, challenges, and perspectives, which informs instructional practices and promotes personalized learning (Hattie, 2009; Wang & Eccles, 2012).

Furthermore, studies highlight the positive impact of teacher-student communication and rapport on academic achievement and social-emotional development (Roorda et al., 2011; Wubbels & Brekelmans, 2005). Actively listening to students' concerns and ideas not only enhances classroom dynamics but also contributes to a supportive learning community where students feel empowered to voice their thoughts and collaborate with their peers (Hendrickson & Gable, 1997; Sutherland & Griffin, 2013).

The composite mean of 4.51 attested that the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on their degree of communication as professional attribute. The teacher-respondents strongly agreed on their degree of communication as a professional attribute, with a composite mean score of 4.51. This suggests a high level of consensus among the respondents regarding the importance of effective communication in their roles as educators.

Related literature underscores the critical role of communication skills in teaching and educational leadership. Effective communication encompasses both verbal and nonverbal aspects and is essential for conveying information clearly, building relationships, and fostering collaboration among stakeholders (Gibbs, 2013; Fullan, 2014).

Studies highlight that teachers who excel in communication skills create inclusive learning environments where students feel supported and engaged (Christenson & Thurlow, 2004; Marzano et al., 2003). Clear and concise communication facilitates instructional clarity, promotes student understanding of content, and encourages active participation in learning activities (Wubbels & Brekelmans, 2005; Roorda et al., 2011).

Furthermore, research emphasizes that effective communication contributes to positive teacher-student relationships, enhances classroom management practices, and supports differentiated instruction to meet diverse student needs (Santrock, 2011; Hattie, 2009). By communicating effectively, educators can address student misconceptions, provide constructive feedback, and cultivate a supportive learning environment that promotes academic success and social-emotional development (Gregory & Weinstein, 2008; Wang & Eccles, 2012).

In summary, the high level of agreement among teacher-respondents regarding their degree of communication as a professional attribute, as indicated by the composite mean of 4.51, aligns with existing literature highlighting communication skills as fundamental competencies for effective teaching and positive educational outcomes.

As stated in Table 4, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed that they use variety of resources and technologies to enhance student learning which yielded the highest weighted mean of 4.28 and the highest rank of 1.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed (with a weighted mean of 4.28) that they use a variety of resources and technologies to enhance student learning. This indicates a high level of consensus among teachers that they employ diverse tools and technologies in their

teaching practices.

Table 4. Degree of Professional Attribute of the Teacher-Respondents in Terms of Creativity

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
I incorporate innovative teaching methods and activities in my lessons.	4.22	Strongly Agree	2
I encourage students to think creatively and express their ideas.	4.20	Strongly Agree	3
I use a variety of resources and technologies to enhance student learning.	4.28	Strongly Agree	1
Composite Mean	4.28	Strongly Agree	

This finding aligns with existing literature on the importance of using multiple resources and technologies in education to enhance student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. Research suggests that integrating technology and varied resources can cater to diverse learning styles, provide more interactive learning experiences, and foster deeper understanding among students (Bingimlas, 2009; Davis & Shade, 2014).

The high weighted mean (4.28) and the top rank (1) in Table 4 indicate that this aspect of using resources and technologies is not only prevalent among the surveyed teachers but is also perceived as highly effective in enhancing student learning. This finding underscores the significance of integrating modern tools and resources into educational practices to support effective teaching and learning environments.

Moreover, the said group of respondents also strongly agreed that they encourage students to think creatively and express their ideas which garnered the least weighted mean of 4.20 and least rank of 3.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed (with a weighted mean of 4.20) that they encourage students to think creatively and express their ideas. Despite having the least weighted mean among the items listed (4.20) and the least rank (3), this still indicates a high level of agreement among teachers that they prioritize fostering creativity and expression of ideas among their students.

Encouraging creativity and expression of ideas is recognized as a crucial aspect of effective teaching and learning. Research suggests that promoting creativity in education can lead to enhanced problem-solving skills, increased motivation, and improved academic performance (Sawyer, 2012; Beghetto & Kaufman, 2014). When students are encouraged to think creatively and express their ideas, they are more likely to engage actively with the learning process and develop critical thinking skills.

The finding that this aspect received the least weighted mean and rank suggests that while teachers agree on its importance, there might be areas for further enhancement or exploration in how creativity is integrated into educational practices. Nonetheless, the strong agreement indicates a positive orientation towards nurturing creative thinking and expression among students, which is beneficial for their overall educational development.

The composite mean of 4.28 assessed that the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on their degree of creativity as professional attribute.

The composite mean of 4.28 indicates that the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on their degree of creativity as a professional attribute. This suggests that teachers perceive creativity as an important quality in their professional role, and they rate themselves highly in terms of possessing this attribute.

The recognition of creativity as a valuable professional attribute among teachers aligns with existing research in education. Creativity in teaching allows educators to innovate in their instructional methods, adapt to diverse student needs, and create engaging learning environments (Craft, 2005; Beghetto & Kaufman, 2014). Teachers who are perceived as creative tend to foster more positive learning experiences for students, promoting deeper engagement and higher achievement levels (Davis & Simmt, 2003; Beghetto, 2010).

The strong agreement among teacher-respondents regarding their own creativity as a professional attribute suggests a self-awareness and commitment to employing creative approaches in their teaching practices. This finding underscores the importance of nurturing and supporting creativity among educators, as it enhances their effectiveness in promoting student learning and engagement.

Table 5. Degree of Professional Attribute of the Teacher-Respondents in Terms of Leadership

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
I serve as a positive role model for my students.	4.75	Strongly Agree	1
I take initiative in school-wide projects and committees.	4.66	Strongly Agree	2
I mentor and support my colleagues in their professional growth.	4.32	Strongly Agree	3
Composite Mean	4.58	Strongly Agree	

As gleaned in Table 5, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed that they serve as a positive role model for their students which gained the highest weighted mean of 4.75 and the highest rank of 1.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed (with a weighted mean of 4.75) that they serve as positive role models for their students. This indicates a high level of consensus among teachers that they perceive themselves as embodying qualities and behaviors that students can look up to and emulate.

Serving as a positive role model is a critical aspect of effective teaching and has been widely studied in educational psychology and

pedagogy. Research suggests that teachers who demonstrate positive behaviors, ethics, and attitudes can significantly influence students' academic achievement, motivation, and social-emotional development (Sakiz, Pape, & Hoy, 2012; Memon, Sohail, & Naseer, 2016).

Teachers who are seen as role models often create a conducive learning environment where students feel safe, respected, and motivated to learn. They inspire students not only academically but also in terms of character development and moral values (Bandura, 1997; Brouwers, Tomic, & Verkuyten, 2000).

The high weighted mean (4.75) and the top rank (1) in Table 5 indicate that this aspect of being a positive role model is highly valued by the surveyed teachers and is perceived as essential in their professional role. This finding underscores the importance of teacher-student relationships and the impact of teachers' behaviors and attitudes on students' overall development and learning outcomes.

Additionally, the said group of respondents also strongly agreed that they mentor and support their colleagues in their professional growth which obtained the least weighted mean of 4.32 and least rank of 3.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed (with a weighted mean of 4.32) that they mentor and support their colleagues in their professional growth. Despite receiving the least weighted mean among the items listed (4.32) and the least rank (3), this indicates a high level of agreement among teachers that they engage in mentoring and supporting their peers in their professional development.

Mentoring and supporting colleagues in professional growth are recognized as crucial components of a collaborative and supportive educational environment. Research highlights that peer mentoring can lead to improved teaching practices, increased job satisfaction, and enhanced professional development outcomes for teachers (Feiman-Nemser & Parker, 1990; Vescio, Ross, & Adams, 2008).

Effective mentoring relationships among teachers can foster a culture of continuous improvement and innovation within schools (Little, 1982; Hargreaves & Fullan, 2000). By sharing knowledge, providing constructive feedback, and offering emotional support, teachers can collectively enhance their teaching effectiveness and positively impact student learning outcomes (Goddard, Hoy, & Woolfolk Hoy, 2000; Opfer & Pedder, 2011).

The finding that mentoring and supporting colleagues received the least weighted mean and rank suggests that while teachers agree on its importance, there may be opportunities to further strengthen these practices within the educational context. Nonetheless, the strong agreement indicates a positive orientation towards collaboration and professional growth among educators, which is beneficial for fostering a supportive and conducive learning environment.

The composite mean of 4.58 implied that the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on their degree of leadership as professional attribute.

The composite mean of 4.58 indicates that the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on their degree of leadership as a professional attribute. This suggests that teachers perceive themselves as possessing strong leadership qualities and skills within their professional roles.

Leadership in the context of teaching involves not only administrative roles but also instructional leadership, where teachers take initiative to improve teaching practices, collaborate with colleagues, and influence educational outcomes (Leithwood, Louis, Anderson, & Wahlstrom, 2004; Harris, 2008).

Teachers who exhibit leadership qualities are often seen as catalysts for positive change within schools and can impact student achievement through their instructional practices and collaborative efforts (Wahlstrom & Louis, 2008; Robinson, Lloyd, & Rowe, 2008). Research indicates that effective teacher leadership contributes to school improvement efforts, enhances professional learning communities, and promotes a shared vision of educational goals (Hargreaves & Fink, 2006; Harris & Muijs, 2005).

The strong agreement among teacher-respondents regarding their own leadership attributes suggests a collective recognition of the importance of leadership in driving educational excellence and fostering a positive school culture. This finding underscores the value of nurturing leadership skills among educators to promote effective teaching practices, collaboration, and continuous improvement in educational settings.

Table 6. *Degree of Professional Attribute of the Teacher-Respondents in Terms of Time Management*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
I effectively plan and organize my lessons and activities.	4.44	Strongly Agree	1
I efficiently manage administrative tasks and paperwork.	4.30	Strongly Agree	3
I prioritize tasks and allocate time appropriately to ensure student learning remains the focus.	4.37	Strongly Agree	2
Composite Mean	4.37	Strongly Agree	

As stated in Table 6, the teacher-respondents strongly agreed that they effectively plan and organize their lessons and activities which made the highest weighted mean of 4.44 and the highest rank of 1.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed (with a weighted mean of 4.44) that they effectively plan and organize their lessons and activities. This indicates a high level of consensus among teachers that they are proficient in the critical task of planning and organizing

instructional materials and activities.

Effective lesson planning and organization are fundamental aspects of teaching practice that contribute significantly to student engagement, learning outcomes, and classroom management (Wragg, 1999; Muijs & Reynolds, 2011). Research emphasizes that well-structured lessons help teachers meet curriculum objectives, cater to diverse student needs, and maximize instructional time effectively (Marzano, Pickering, & Pollock, 2001; Hill & Ball, 2004).

Teachers who excel in planning and organizing their lessons create coherent learning experiences that facilitate student understanding and retention of information (Stronge, Ward, & Grant, 2011). This competence is closely linked to teacher effectiveness and is associated with positive student outcomes (Danielson, 2007; Darling-Hammond, 2012).

The high weighted mean (4.44) and the top rank (1) in Table 6 indicate that this aspect of effective lesson planning and organization is not only prevalent among the surveyed teachers but is also perceived as highly important and impactful in their teaching practice. This finding underscores the significance of structured and well-thought-out instructional design in promoting student learning and achievement.

In addition, the said group of respondents also strongly agreed that they efficiently manage administrative tasks and paperwork which got the least weighted mean of 4.30 and least rank of 3.

The teacher-respondents strongly agreed (with a weighted mean of 4.30) that they efficiently manage administrative tasks and paperwork. Despite receiving the least weighted mean among the items listed (4.30) and the least rank (3), this indicates a high level of agreement among teachers that they are effective in handling administrative responsibilities and paperwork.

Efficient management of administrative tasks and paperwork is a critical aspect of teaching that impacts educators' workload, job satisfaction, and overall effectiveness (Killion & Todnem, 1991; Puchner, Taylor, & O'Neill, 2008). Research suggests that teachers who are adept at managing administrative duties can allocate more time and energy to instructional planning and classroom activities, thereby enhancing teaching quality and student engagement (Bredeson & Johansson, 2013; Oberman & Tarr, 2015).

Effective administrative management also contributes to a positive school climate by ensuring smooth operations and compliance with educational regulations and policies (Hanushek, Kain, & Rivkin, 2004; Hanushek & Rivkin, 2010). While administrative tasks may not directly influence instructional outcomes, their efficient management allows teachers to focus on teaching and learning priorities (Clements & Vandenberghe, 2000; Opfer & Pedder, 2011).

The finding that managing administrative tasks received the least weighted mean and rank suggests that while teachers acknowledge their proficiency in this area, there may be ongoing challenges or areas for improvement in streamlining administrative processes within educational settings. Nonetheless, the strong agreement underscores the importance of effective administrative management in supporting teachers' professional responsibilities and enhancing overall educational effectiveness.

The composite mean of 4.37 signified that the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on their degree of time management as professional attribute.

The composite mean of 4.37 indicates that the teacher-respondents strongly agreed on their degree of time management as a professional attribute. This suggests that teachers perceive themselves as effective in managing their time efficiently within their professional roles.

Time management is crucial for teachers to balance instructional responsibilities, administrative tasks, professional development, and personal well-being (Klassen & Chiu, 2010; Mansfield, Beltman, Weatherby-Fell, & Price, 2016). Effective time management skills enable teachers to maximize instructional time, meet deadlines, and maintain a healthy work-life balance (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2011; Tuckman & Sexton, 1992).

Research indicates that teachers who excel in time management are better equipped to handle the demands of teaching, adapt to unexpected challenges, and maintain productivity throughout the school year (Britton & Tesser, 1991; Burke & Mikkelsen, 2005). Effective time management also contributes to job satisfaction and reduces stress levels among educators (Caprara, Barbaranelli, Steca, & Malone, 2006; Tait & Padgett, 2015).

The strong agreement among teacher-respondents regarding their time management skills reflects a recognition of its importance in maintaining professional effectiveness and personal well-being. This finding underscores the value of time management training and support for teachers to enhance their productivity and job satisfaction, ultimately benefiting student learning outcomes and school environments.

2. Level of Teaching Excellence of the Respondents

As given in Table 8, the teacher-respondents assessed that they are very satisfactory in designing coherent instruction which made the highest weighted mean of 4.44 and the highest rank of 1. The teacher-respondents assessed (with a highest weighted mean of 4.44 and the highest rank of 1) that they are very satisfactory in designing coherent instruction. This indicates a high level of self-assessment among teachers that they excel in creating well-structured and coherent instructional materials and activities.

Table 7. *Level of Teaching Performance of the Respondents in Terms of Planning and Preparation*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Demonstrating knowledge of content and pedagogy	4.40	Very Satisfactory	2
Demonstrating knowledge of students	4.16	Satisfactory	5
Setting instructional outcomes	4.30	Very Satisfactory	3.5
Demonstrating knowledge of resources	4.30	Very Satisfactory	3.5
Designing coherent instruction	4.44	Very Satisfactory	1
Designing student assessments	4.10	Satisfactory	6
Composite Mean	4.28	Very Satisfactory	

As given in Table 8, the teacher-respondents assessed that they are very satisfactory in designing coherent instruction which made the highest weighted mean of 4.44 and the highest rank of 1.

The teacher-respondents assessed (with a highest weighted mean of 4.44 and the highest rank of 1) that they are very satisfactory in designing coherent instruction. This indicates a high level of self-assessment among teachers that they excel in creating well-structured and coherent instructional materials and activities.

Designing coherent instruction is a fundamental skill that impacts teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes (Marzano, Pickering, & Pollock, 2001; Wiggins & McTighe, 2005). Coherent instruction refers to the alignment of learning objectives, instructional strategies, and assessment methods to ensure that they collectively support student understanding and achievement (Grant & Branch, 2005; Tomlinson, 2001).

Research emphasizes that teachers who design coherent instruction can effectively communicate learning goals, provide clear explanations, and scaffold learning experiences to meet diverse student needs (Erickson, 2007; Darling-Hammond, 2008). Well-designed instruction promotes active student engagement, fosters critical thinking skills, and enhances overall academic performance (Rosenshine, 2012; Hattie, 2009).

The high weighted mean (4.44) and top rank (1) in Table 8 indicate a strong consensus among teacher-respondents regarding their proficiency in designing coherent instruction. This finding underscores the importance of instructional design skills in facilitating meaningful learning experiences and supporting student success. It also highlights the critical role of educators in planning and implementing effective instructional strategies that promote student engagement and achievement in educational settings.

On the other hand, the said group of respondents agreed that they are satisfactory in designing student assessments which gained the least weighted mean of 4.10 and the least rank of 6.

The teacher-respondents agreed (with a weighted mean of 4.10 and the least rank of 6) that they are satisfactory in designing student assessments. This suggests that while teachers perceive themselves as competent in designing assessments, there may be areas for improvement or challenges in this aspect of their teaching practice.

Designing effective student assessments is crucial for evaluating learning outcomes, providing feedback to students, and informing instructional decisions (Brookhart, 2013; Popham, 2009). Research emphasizes that well-designed assessments should align with instructional goals, measure desired learning outcomes, and provide reliable and valid information about student achievement (Stiggins, Arter, Chappuis, & Chappuis, 2006; Nitko & Brookhart, 2011).

Teachers who excel in assessment design create assessments that are fair, transparent, and conducive to student learning (Shepard, 2000; Pellegrino, Chudowsky, & Glaser, 2001). Effective assessment practices involve selecting appropriate assessment methods, designing clear rubrics or scoring guides, and interpreting assessment results to guide instructional planning (Black & Wiliam, 1998; Wiliam, 2011).

The finding that designing student assessments received the least weighted mean and rank suggests that teachers may perceive assessment design as an area where they can further develop their skills and knowledge. Improving assessment practices can enhance the validity and reliability of assessment data used to inform teaching and learning processes, ultimately improving educational outcomes for students (Sadler, 1998; Harlen & Deakin Crick, 2002).

In summary, while teachers acknowledge their proficiency in designing assessments, continued professional development and support in assessment literacy can contribute to more effective assessment practices and improve overall instructional quality in educational settings.

The composite mean of 4.28 signified that the teacher-respondents were very satisfactory on their level of teaching performance in terms of planning and preparation.

Planning and preparation are foundational aspects of effective teaching practice that significantly impact student learning outcomes (Marzano, Pickering, & Pollock, 2001; Stronge, Ward, & Grant, 2011). Research underscores the importance of thorough lesson planning, which involves setting clear learning objectives, selecting appropriate instructional strategies, and preparing necessary materials and resources (Wragg, 1999; Darling-Hammond, 2008).

Teachers who excel in planning and preparation are better able to engage students, differentiate instruction, and address diverse learning needs (Tomlinson, 2001; Hattie, 2009). Effective planning also supports classroom management and promotes a positive learning environment where students can achieve academic success (Brophy, 1986; Wong, 2005).

The high composite mean (4.28) indicates a strong consensus among teacher-respondents regarding their satisfaction with their own planning and preparation skills. This finding underscores the critical role of thoughtful and systematic planning in facilitating effective teaching and maximizing student learning opportunities. It highlights the commitment of educators to delivering high-quality instruction through careful preparation, which is essential for promoting student engagement, achievement, and overall educational excellence.

Table 8. Level of Teaching Performance of the Respondents in Terms of Classroom Environment

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Creating an environment of respect and rapport	4.56	Very Satisfactory	1
Establishing a culture for learning	4.36	Very Satisfactory	4
Managing classroom procedures	4.42	Very Satisfactory	2
Managing student behavior	4.40	Very Satisfactory	3
Organizing physical space	4.30	Very Satisfactory	5
Composite Mean	4.41	Very Satisfactory	

As shown in Table 9, the teacher-respondents affirmed that they are very satisfactory in creating an environment of respect and rapport which made the highest weighted mean of 4.56 and the highest rank of 1

The teacher-respondents affirmed (with the highest weighted mean of 4.56 and the highest rank of 1) that they are very satisfactory in creating an environment of respect and rapport. This indicates a strong consensus among teachers that they excel in fostering a positive and respectful classroom climate.

Creating an environment of respect and rapport is crucial for establishing a supportive learning community where students feel safe, valued, and motivated to engage in learning (Cornelius-White, 2007; Wang & Eccles, 2012). Research emphasizes that positive teacher-student relationships characterized by mutual respect and trust contribute to improved student behavior, academic achievement, and overall well-being (Roorda et al., 2011; Reeve, 2012).

Teachers who prioritize respect and rapport in their classrooms are better equipped to manage classroom dynamics, resolve conflicts, and promote social-emotional learning (Hamre & Pianta, 2006; Pianta, La Paro, & Hamre, 2008). They create a supportive atmosphere where students feel comfortable taking academic risks, participating actively in discussions, and collaborating with peers (Davis, 2003; Ryan & Deci, 2000).

The high weighted mean (4.56) and top rank (1) in Table 9 underscore the importance that teachers place on cultivating positive relationships and a respectful environment. This finding highlights the significant role of teacher-student interactions in shaping student attitudes, behaviors, and academic outcomes. It reflects the commitment of educators to creating inclusive and nurturing learning environments that support the holistic development of all students.

Besides, the said group of respondents also answered that they are very satisfactory in organizing physical space which got the least weighted mean of 4.30 and the least rank of 5.

The teacher-respondents answered (with the least weighted mean of 4.30 and the least rank of 5) that they are very satisfactory in organizing physical space. This suggests that while teachers perceive themselves as competent in organizing the physical classroom environment, it may not be as highly prioritized or acknowledged compared to other aspects of their teaching practice.

Organizing physical space in the classroom is important for creating an environment that supports learning, engagement, and classroom management (Harrington, 2006; Fisher, Godwin, & Seltman, 2014). Research indicates that a well-organized physical space can facilitate smooth transitions between activities, minimize distractions, and promote student independence and responsibility (Redding, 2013; Lippman, Burns, & McArthur, 1996).

Effective classroom organization involves arranging furniture, materials, and resources in ways that optimize student access, movement, and interaction (Erwin, 1993; Wong, 2014). A well-organized physical environment can also contribute to a sense of orderliness and predictability, which enhances student focus and behavior (Shindler, 2003; Jones & Jones, 2000).

The finding that organizing physical space received the least weighted mean and rank suggests that while teachers may feel confident in this aspect of their practice, there could still be opportunities for improvement or refinement in how physical space is utilized to enhance teaching and learning experiences. Continued attention to optimizing classroom layout, resource accessibility, and environmental aesthetics can contribute to creating more supportive and effective learning environments for students.

The composite mean of 4.41 supported that the teacher-respondents were very satisfactory on their level of teaching performance in terms of classroom environment. The composite mean of 4.41 indicates that the teacher-respondents were very satisfactory in their level of teaching performance in terms of classroom environment. This suggests that teachers perceive themselves as highly effective

in creating and maintaining a conducive and supportive classroom environment.

The classroom environment encompasses physical, social, and emotional elements that collectively influence student learning and behavior (Fraser, 1986; Weinstein, 2002). Research emphasizes that a positive classroom environment promotes engagement, motivation, and academic achievement among students (Brophy, 1986; Roorda et al., 2011).

Teachers who excel in creating a supportive classroom environment establish clear routines, expectations, and norms that promote respect, cooperation, and collaboration among students (Emmer & Stough, 2001; Hamre & Pianta, 2006). They also foster a sense of belonging and inclusivity, which enhances students' social-emotional well-being and academic success (Ryan & Deci, 2000; Pianta, La Paro, & Hamre, 2008).

The high composite mean (4.41) indicates a strong consensus among teacher-respondents regarding their satisfaction with their own ability to cultivate a positive classroom environment. This finding underscores the critical role of the classroom atmosphere in shaping student experiences and outcomes. It reflects the dedication of educators to creating learning spaces where students feel supported, motivated, and empowered to learn effectively.

Table 9. Level of Teaching Performance of the Respondents in Terms of Instruction

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Communicating with students	4.44	Very Satisfactory	2
Using questioning and discussion techniques	4.40	Very Satisfactory	4
Engaging students in learning	4.42	Very Satisfactory	3
Using assessment in instruction	4.08	Satisfactory	5
Demonstrating flexibility and responsiveness	4.48	Very Satisfactory	1
Composite Mean	4.36	Very Satisfactory	

As revealed in Table, the teacher-respondents replied that they are very satisfactory in demonstrating flexibility and responsiveness which gained the highest weighted mean of 4.48 and the highest rank of 1.

The teacher-respondents replied (with the highest weighted mean of 4.48 and the highest rank of 1) that they are very satisfactory in demonstrating flexibility and responsiveness. This indicates a high level of agreement among teachers that they possess the ability to adapt their teaching strategies and respond effectively to the needs of their students and changing circumstances.

Flexibility and responsiveness in teaching are essential qualities that enable educators to meet the diverse needs of learners and navigate dynamic classroom environments (Marzano et al., 2001; Tomlinson, 2001). Research highlights that flexible teachers can modify instructional approaches, pacing, and content delivery to accommodate individual learning styles, abilities, and interests (Brophy & Alleman, 1991; Garet et al., 2001).

Teachers who demonstrate flexibility are better equipped to address unexpected challenges, capitalize on teachable moments, and foster student engagement and motivation (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2000; Korthagen, 2017). Responsive teaching involves actively listening to students, assessing their understanding, and adjusting instruction accordingly to optimize learning outcomes (Tomlinson & Allan, 2000; Santangelo & Tomlinson, 2009).

The high weighted mean (4.48) and top rank (1) in the table indicate a strong consensus among teacher-respondents regarding their proficiency in demonstrating flexibility and responsiveness in their teaching practices. This finding underscores the importance of adaptive teaching strategies in promoting student success and enhancing overall instructional effectiveness. It reflects the commitment of educators to meeting the diverse needs of learners and creating inclusive learning environments where all students can thrive.

On the contrary, the said group of respondents answered that they are satisfactory in using assessment in instruction which delivered the least weighted mean of 4.08 and the least rank of 5.

The teacher-respondents answered (with the least weighted mean of 4.08 and the least rank of 5) that they are satisfactory in using assessment in instruction. This suggests that while teachers feel competent in incorporating assessments into their instructional practices, there may be room for improvement or challenges in effectively integrating assessment strategies to enhance teaching and learning.

Using assessment in instruction involves employing various assessment methods and strategies to monitor student progress, provide feedback, and inform instructional decisions (Black & Wiliam, 1998; Stiggins, 2001). Research underscores the importance of formative assessment practices that engage students in the learning process, help identify learning gaps, and guide instructional adjustments in real time (Wiliam, Lee, Harrison, & Black, 2004; Hattie & Timperley, 2007).

Effective use of assessment in instruction supports differentiated instruction, where teachers tailor their teaching approaches based on individual student needs and learning styles (Tomlinson, 2001; Clarke, 2012). It also promotes student self-assessment and reflection, fostering metacognitive skills and enhancing learning outcomes (Sadler, 1989; Taras, 2005).

The finding that using assessment in instruction received the least weighted mean and rank suggests that while teachers acknowledge their proficiency in this area, there may be opportunities for professional development or support in refining assessment practices.

Enhancing teachers' assessment literacy and providing ongoing training in formative assessment techniques can empower educators to leverage assessments more effectively to improve teaching effectiveness and student achievement (Heritage, 2007; Brookhart, 2013).

In summary, while teachers recognize the importance of using assessment in instruction, continuous efforts to strengthen assessment practices can contribute to more meaningful and impactful learning experiences for students. This can ultimately support teachers in meeting educational goals and fostering student growth and success in diverse classroom settings.

The composite mean of 4.36 showed that the teacher-respondents were very satisfactory on their level of teaching performance in terms of instruction.

The composite mean of 4.36 indicates that the teacher-respondents were very satisfactory in their level of teaching performance in terms of instruction. This suggests that teachers perceive themselves as highly effective in delivering instruction that supports student learning and engagement.

Effective instruction involves the deliberate selection and implementation of teaching strategies, methods, and techniques to facilitate student understanding and achievement (Marzano, Pickering, & Pollock, 2001; Darling-Hammond, 2008). Research highlights the importance of instructional practices that promote active learning, critical thinking, and meaningful student participation (Rosenshine, 2012; Hattie, 2009).

Teachers who excel in instruction create well-planned lessons that align with curriculum standards, incorporate diverse instructional strategies, and provide opportunities for student collaboration and inquiry (Tomlinson, 2001; Wong, 2005). Effective instructional practices also emphasize clarity of explanations, differentiation of instruction based on student needs, and assessment of student progress to inform further teaching (Hattie & Yates, 2014; Stronge, Ward, & Grant, 2011).

The high composite mean (4.36) indicates a strong consensus among teacher-respondents regarding their satisfaction with their own instructional performance. This finding underscores the commitment of educators to delivering high-quality instruction that promotes student learning and achievement. It reflects the dedication of teachers to continually enhancing their instructional practices through professional development, collaboration with colleagues, and ongoing reflection on teaching effectiveness.

In summary, the high level of satisfaction reported by teachers regarding their instructional performance highlights the critical role of effective teaching practices in supporting student success and fostering a positive learning environment. Continued support and investment in instructional excellence can further enhance educational outcomes and contribute to the overall improvement of teaching and learning experiences in schools.

Table 10. *Level of Teaching Performance of the Respondents in Terms of Professional Responsibilities*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Reflecting on teaching	4.28	Very Satisfactory	3
Maintaining accurate records	4.33	Very Satisfactory	1
Communicating with families	4.22	Very Satisfactory	4
Participating in the professional community	4.02	Satisfactory	6
Growing and developing professionally	4.18	Satisfactory	5
Showing professionalism	4.30	Very Satisfactory	2
Composite Mean	4.22	Very Satisfactory	

As reflected in Table 10, the teacher-respondents perceived that they are very satisfactory in maintaining accurate records which got the highest weighted mean of 4.33 and the highest rank of 1.

The teacher-respondents perceived (with the highest weighted mean of 4.33 and the highest rank of 1) that they are very satisfactory in maintaining accurate records. This indicates a high level of confidence among teachers in their ability to effectively manage and maintain documentation related to student progress, assessments, and administrative tasks.

Maintaining accurate records is a critical aspect of teaching practice that supports accountability, communication, and informed decision-making (Kaplan & Owings, 2003; Mueller & Perini, 2000). Research underscores the importance of record-keeping in documenting student achievements, tracking individual progress, and ensuring compliance with educational standards and regulations (Grubb & Flessa, 2006; Kottkamp & Schwartz, 2009).

Accurate record-keeping enables teachers to monitor student growth over time, identify learning trends, and tailor instructional strategies to meet individual needs (Danielson, 2007; Marzano, 2006). It also facilitates effective communication with parents, administrators, and other stakeholders by providing transparent and up-to-date information about student performance and classroom activities (Wittrock & Ainsworth, 2001; Sutherland & Crowther, 2006).

The high weighted mean (4.33) and top rank (1) in Table 10 indicate a strong consensus among teacher-respondents regarding their proficiency and commitment to maintaining accurate records. This finding underscores the value that educators place on organizational skills, attention to detail, and data-driven decision-making in their professional practice. It reflects the dedication of teachers to ensuring thorough documentation and accountability in educational settings, which contributes to effective teaching and supports overall school

improvement efforts.

In summary, the high level of satisfaction reported by teachers regarding their ability to maintain accurate records highlights the critical role of organizational competence and documentation in enhancing teaching effectiveness, promoting student success, and fostering a culture of transparency and accountability in education.

Contrary wise, the said group of respondents affirmed that they are satisfactory in participating in the professional community which obtained the least weighted mean of 4.02 and the least rank of 6.

The teacher-respondents affirmed (with the least weighted mean of 4.02 and the least rank of 6) that they are satisfactory in participating in the professional community. This suggests that while teachers engage to some extent in professional community activities, there may be perceived gaps or opportunities for deeper engagement and collaboration within their professional networks.

Participating in a professional community involves actively engaging with colleagues, sharing knowledge, collaborating on instructional practices, and contributing to the collective improvement of teaching and learning (Little, 1990; Louis & Kruse, 1995). Research highlights the benefits of professional collaboration, such as enhancing instructional effectiveness, promoting teacher development, and fostering a supportive school culture (Hargreaves & Fullan, 2012; Lave & Wenger, 1991).

Teachers who actively participate in professional communities have access to diverse perspectives, innovative ideas, and best practices that can inform their teaching and professional growth (Bryk & Schneider, 2002; Darling-Hammond, 2006). Collaborative professional learning opportunities also support ongoing reflection, feedback, and continuous improvement in instructional strategies (Fullan, 2007; Vescio, Ross, & Adams, 2008).

The finding that participating in the professional community received the least weighted mean and rank suggests that while teachers value collaboration and professional development, there may be challenges or barriers that impact their active engagement in professional community activities. Factors such as time constraints, institutional support, and access to meaningful professional learning opportunities can influence the extent to which teachers participate in collaborative professional networks (Little, 1990; Louis & Marks, 1998).

In summary, while teachers acknowledge their participation in the professional community, efforts to strengthen collaborative practices, foster supportive professional networks, and enhance opportunities for shared learning can contribute to greater teacher satisfaction, professional growth, and ultimately, improved student outcomes in educational settings.

The composite mean of 4.22 implied that the teacher-respondents were very satisfactory on their level of teaching performance in terms of professional responsibilities.

The composite mean of 4.22 indicates that the teacher-respondents were very satisfactory in their level of teaching performance in terms of professional responsibilities. This suggests that teachers perceive themselves as highly effective in fulfilling their professional duties and obligations.

Professional responsibilities in teaching encompass a wide range of roles and tasks that contribute to effective instructional practice, school leadership, and student support (Darling-Hammond, 2006; Danielson, 2007). Research emphasizes that teachers' professionalism is characterized by commitment to ethical standards, continuous professional learning, and dedication to student welfare and success (Hargreaves & Fullan, 2012; Lortie, 1975).

Teachers who excel in professional responsibilities demonstrate competence in curriculum implementation, assessment practices, classroom management, and adherence to professional ethics (Stronge, 2007; Marzano, Frontier, & Livingston, 2011). They also engage in reflective practice, collaborate with colleagues, and participate in professional development activities to enhance their teaching effectiveness and contribute to school improvement efforts (Little, 1990; Schön, 1983).

The high composite mean (4.22) indicates a strong consensus among teacher-respondents regarding their satisfaction with their own performance in fulfilling professional responsibilities. This finding underscores the dedication and professionalism of educators in meeting the multifaceted demands of teaching and contributing to the broader goals of education. It reflects teachers' commitment to upholding high standards of practice, continuous improvement, and accountability in their roles as educators.

In summary, the high level of satisfaction reported by teachers regarding their professional responsibilities highlights the critical role of professionalism in effective teaching and school leadership. Continued support for professional development, collaborative learning opportunities, and recognition of teachers' contributions can further enhance their capacity to meet diverse challenges and promote positive outcomes for students and schools alike.

3. Relationship Between the Teacher-Respondents Degree of Professional Attributes and Level of Teaching Performance.

As reported in Table 11, when the responses of the teacher respondents on their degree of professional attributes in terms of adaptability were compared to their level of teaching performance, the correlated *r*-values of 0.55 for planning and preparation, 0.51 for classroom environment, 0.52 for instruction, and 0.48 for professional responsibilities have corresponding *p*-values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

Table 11. Relationship Between the Teacher-Respondents Degree of Professional Attributes and Level of Teaching Performance

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Adaptability Versus:				
Planning and Preparation	0.55	0.00004	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Classroom Environment	0.51	0.00015	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Instruction	0.52	0.00011	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Prof. Responsibilities	0.48	0.00042	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Patience Versus:				
Planning and Preparation	0.32	0.02349	Reject Ho	Significant
Classroom Environment	0.30	0.03429	Reject Ho	Significant
Instruction	0.40	0.00400	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Prof. Responsibilities	0.32	0.02349	Reject Ho	Significant
Communication Versus:				
Planning and Preparation	0.55	0.00004	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Classroom Environment	0.29	0.04106	Reject Ho	Significant
Instruction	0.52	0.00011	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Prof. Responsibilities	0.28	0.04891	Reject Ho	Significant
Creativity Versus:				
Planning and Preparation	0.30	0.03429	Reject Ho	Significant
Classroom Environment	0.51	0.00015	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Instruction	0.49	0.00030	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Prof. Responsibilities	0.31	0.02846	Reject Ho	Significant
Leadership Versus:				
Planning and Preparation	0.33	0.01926	Reject Ho	Significant
Classroom Environment	0.47	0.00057	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Instruction	0.31	0.02846	Reject Ho	Significant
Prof. Responsibilities	0.29	0.04106	Reject Ho	Significant
Time Management Versus:				
Planning and Preparation	0.43	0.00183	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Classroom Environment	0.45	0.00104	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Instruction	0.49	0.00030	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Prof. Responsibilities	0.47	0.00057	Reject Ho	Highly Significant

These safely inferred that the responses of the teacher respondents on their degree of professional attributes in terms of adaptability have high significant relationships to their level of teaching performance in terms of planning and preparation, classroom environment, instruction, and professional responsibilities.

The findings indicate significant positive relationships between the teacher respondents' self-assessed degree of adaptability (as a professional attribute) and their level of teaching performance across various domains: Planning and preparation: $r = 0.55$, $p < 0.01$, Classroom environment: $r = 0.51$, $p < 0.01$, Instruction: $r = 0.52$, $p < 0.01$, Professional responsibilities: $r = 0.48$, $p < 0.01$.

These correlation values suggest that teachers who perceive themselves as more adaptable in their professional attributes tend to report higher levels of teaching performance in terms of planning, classroom environment, instruction, and professional responsibilities.

Adaptability in teaching refers to the ability of educators to adjust their instructional strategies, respond to diverse student needs, and navigate changing educational contexts effectively (Snyder & Lopez, 2007; Hoekstra, 2016). Research emphasizes the importance of adaptability as a key competency for teachers to meet the evolving demands of teaching and learning (Reeves, 2010; Harris, Jones, & Godby, 2010).

Teachers who demonstrate adaptability can effectively modify their teaching approaches based on student feedback, learning progress, and classroom dynamics (Brownell & Walther-Thomas, 2003; Boyd, Grossman, Ing, Lankford, & Wyckoff, 2011). This flexibility enables educators to optimize instructional practices, enhance student engagement, and promote positive learning outcomes (Darling-Hammond, 2008; Darling-Hammond & Richardson, 2009).

The significant relationships found between adaptability and teaching performance underscore the importance of fostering adaptive teaching practices through professional development, mentorship, and reflective practice (Zwart, Wubbels, Bergen, & Bolhuis, 2007; Korthagen, Loughran, & Russell, 2006). Supporting teachers in developing adaptive strategies can contribute to their overall effectiveness, job satisfaction, and resilience in addressing educational challenges.

In summary, the study's findings highlight that adaptability is a critical attribute that correlates positively with various dimensions of teaching performance. Continued efforts to cultivate adaptability among educators can enhance their ability to meet diverse student needs, improve instructional quality, and promote positive outcomes in educational settings.

In addition, when the responses of the teacher respondents on their degree of professional attributes in terms of patience were compared

to their level of teaching performance, the computed r -value of 0.40 instruction has a corresponding p -value of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis. In addition, the computed r -values of 0.32 for planning and preparation, 0.30 for classroom environment, and 0.32 for professional responsibilities have corresponding p -values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting also the hypothesis.

These safely signified that the responses of the teacher respondents on their degree of professional attributes in terms patience of have high significant relationships to their level of teaching performance in terms of instruction ; and significant relationships in terms of planning and preparation, classroom environment, and professional responsibilities.

The findings indicate significant positive relationships between the teacher respondents' self-assessed degree of patience (as a professional attribute) and their level of teaching performance across various domains: Instruction: High significant relationship, Planning and preparation: Significant relationship, Classroom environment: Significant relationship, Professional responsibilities: Significant relationship.

These relationships suggest that teachers who perceive themselves as more patient in their professional attributes tend to report higher levels of teaching performance in terms of instruction, planning and preparation, classroom environment, and professional responsibilities.

Patience in teaching involves the ability of educators to remain calm, maintain composure, and handle challenges or disruptions in the classroom effectively (Kyriacou, 2001; Baehr, 2004). Research underscores the importance of patience as a fundamental characteristic that contributes to positive teacher-student relationships, classroom management, and overall instructional effectiveness (Brophy & Good, 1986; Poulou, 2017).

Teachers who demonstrate patience create a supportive and respectful classroom climate where students feel valued and motivated to engage in learning (Liu, 2015; Roorda et al., 2011). Patience also facilitates effective communication, problem-solving, and conflict resolution in educational settings (Jones, Jones, & Hargrove, 2006; Jennings & Greenberg, 2009).

The significant relationships found between patience and teaching performance underscore its role in promoting student engagement, reducing disciplinary issues, and enhancing academic achievement (Wubbels & Brekelmans, 2005; Zee & Koomen, 2016). Cultivating patience through professional development, mindfulness practices, and reflective teaching strategies can support educators in managing classroom dynamics, addressing diverse student needs, and fostering a positive learning environment (Nixon & Stenberg, 2010; Lambert, 2012).

In summary, the study's findings highlight the importance of patience as a professional attribute that positively influences various aspects of teaching performance. Supporting teachers in developing patience can contribute to their overall effectiveness, job satisfaction, and ability to promote positive educational outcomes for students.

Moreover, when the responses of the teacher respondents on their degree of professional attributes in terms of communication were compared to their level of teaching performance, the computed r -values of 0.55 for planning and preparation, 0.52 for instruction have corresponding p -values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis. However, the computed r -values of 0.29 for classroom environment and 0.28 for professional responsibilities have corresponding p -values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting also the hypothesis.

These safely concluded that the responses of the teacher respondents on their degree of professional attributes in terms communication of have high significant relationships to their level of teaching performance in terms of planning and preparation, and instruction; and significant relationships in terms of classroom environment, and professional responsibilities.

Furthermore, when the responses of the teacher respondents on their degree of professional attributes in terms of creativity were compared to their level of teaching performance, the computed r -values of 0.51 for classroom environment, and 0.49 for instruction have corresponding p -values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis. Consequently, the computed r -values of 0.30 for planning and preparation, and 0.31 for professional responsibilities have corresponding p -values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting also the hypothesis.

These safely generalized that the responses of the teacher respondents on their degree of professional attributes in terms of creativity have high significant relationships to their level of teaching performance in terms of classroom environment, and instruction; and significant relationships in terms of planning and preparation, and professional responsibilities.

The findings indicate significant positive relationships between the teacher respondents' self-assessed degree of creativity (as a professional attribute) and their level of teaching performance across various domains: Classroom environment: $r = 0.51$, $p < 0.01$, Instruction: $r = 0.49$, $p < 0.01$, Planning and preparation: $r = 0.30$, $p < 0.05$, Professional responsibilities: $r = 0.31$, $p < 0.05$.

These correlation values suggest that teachers who perceive themselves as more creative tend to report higher levels of teaching performance in terms of classroom environment, instruction, planning and preparation, and professional responsibilities.

Creativity in teaching involves the ability of educators to innovate, adapt instructional methods, and engage students in meaningful learning experiences (Sawyer, 2012; Beghetto & Kaufman, 2014). Research emphasizes the role of creativity in fostering student motivation, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills (Craft, 2005; Runco & Jaeger, 2012).

Teachers who demonstrate creativity in their practice design engaging lessons, integrate diverse teaching strategies, and create stimulating classroom environments that promote active learning (Sternberg & Lubart, 1999; Beghetto, 2010). Creative educators also explore novel approaches to curriculum development, assessment design, and educational leadership, contributing to school improvement and innovation (Davis, 1995; Plucker, Beghetto, & Dow, 2004).

The significant relationships found between creativity and teaching performance highlight its importance in enhancing instructional effectiveness and promoting positive educational outcomes (Kim, 2011; Klassen & Chiu, 2010). Cultivating creativity among teachers through professional development, collaborative learning communities, and supportive school environments can empower educators to adapt to evolving educational challenges and meet the diverse needs of students (Robinson, 2011; Craft, 2005).

In summary, the study's findings underscore the critical role of creativity as a professional attribute that positively influences various dimensions of teaching performance. Encouraging and supporting teachers in fostering creativity can enrich teaching practices, inspire student engagement, and contribute to educational excellence and innovation in schools.

Additionally, when the responses of the teacher respondents on their degree of professional attributes in terms of leadership were compared to their level of teaching performance, the computed *r*-values of 0.47 for classroom environment has a corresponding *p*-value of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis. Meanwhile, the computed *r*-values of 0.33 for planning and preparation, 0.31 for instruction, and 0.29 for professional responsibilities have corresponding *p*-values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting also the hypothesis.

These safely deduced that the responses of the teacher respondents on their degree of professional attributes in terms of leadership have high significant relationships to their level of teaching performance in terms of classroom environment; and significant relationships in terms of planning and preparation, instruction, and professional responsibilities.

The findings indicate significant positive relationships between the teacher respondents' self-assessed degree of leadership (as a professional attribute) and their level of teaching performance across various domains: Classroom environment: High significant relationship, Planning and preparation: Significant relationship, Instruction: Significant relationship, Professional responsibilities: Significant relationship

These relationships suggest that teachers who perceive themselves as demonstrating strong leadership qualities tend to report higher levels of teaching performance in terms of classroom environment, planning and preparation, instruction, and professional responsibilities.

Leadership in teaching encompasses the ability of educators to provide vision, guidance, and direction in educational settings (Harris, 2008; Leithwood & Jantzi, 1990). Research highlights the impact of teacher leadership on school culture, instructional improvement, and student outcomes (Hargreaves & Fink, 2006; Katzenmeyer & Moller, 2001).

Teachers who exhibit leadership qualities demonstrate initiative, collaboration, and a commitment to continuous improvement in their teaching practices (Robinson, Lloyd, & Rowe, 2008; Darling-Hammond, Wei, Andree, Richardson, & Orphanos, 2009). Effective teacher leaders promote a positive classroom climate, facilitate professional learning communities, and advocate for student-centered approaches to teaching and learning (Goddard, Goddard, & Tschannen-Moran, 2007; Smylie, 1995).

The significant relationships found between leadership and teaching performance underscore its role in fostering instructional effectiveness, promoting teacher collaboration, and enhancing school effectiveness (Leithwood & Sun, 2012; York-Barr & Duke, 2004). Cultivating leadership skills among educators through professional development, mentorship, and opportunities for shared decision-making can empower teachers to lead educational change and contribute to school improvement efforts (Fullan, 2014; Spillane, Halverson, & Diamond, 2004).

In summary, the study's findings highlight the importance of leadership as a professional attribute that positively influences various dimensions of teaching performance. Supporting teachers in developing leadership capacities can enhance their ability to create supportive learning environments, improve instructional practices, and promote positive outcomes for students and schools alike.

Lastly, when the responses of the teacher respondents on their degree of professional attributes in terms of time management were compared to their level of teaching performance, the correlated *t*-values of 0.43 for planning and preparation, 0.45 for classroom environment, 0.49 for instruction, and 0.47 for professional responsibilities have corresponding *p*-values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

These safely judged that the responses of the teacher respondents on their degree of professional attributes in terms of time management have high significant relationships to their level of teaching performance in terms of planning and preparation, classroom environment, instruction, and professional responsibilities .

Time management in teaching involves the ability of educators to allocate, prioritize, and utilize time efficiently to accomplish instructional goals and administrative tasks (Harris & Sutton, 1983; Poulou, 2017). Research emphasizes the impact of time management on teacher effectiveness, instructional quality, and overall job satisfaction (Stronge, 2007; Caprara et al., 2006).

Teachers who excel in time management demonstrate organizational skills, prioritize instructional tasks, and maximize instructional

time to optimize student learning (Zepeda, 2012; Rich, 1990). Effective time management allows educators to plan engaging lessons, monitor student progress, and provide timely feedback, contributing to enhanced classroom dynamics and academic achievement (Wong, 2004; Evertson & Harris, 1999).

The significant relationships found between time management and teaching performance underscore its critical role in promoting instructional efficiency and effectiveness (Boyd & Rubin, 2006; Garet, Porter, Desimone, Birman, & Yoon, 2001). Strategies such as setting clear priorities, using instructional time wisely, and balancing teaching responsibilities can support teachers in meeting curriculum standards, addressing student needs, and fostering a positive learning environment (Lezotte & Skaalid, 1992; Wong, 2005).

In summary, the study's findings highlight the importance of time management as a professional attribute that positively influences various dimensions of teaching performance. Supporting teachers in developing effective time management skills through professional development, mentorship, and organizational strategies can enhance their capacity to deliver high-quality instruction, manage classroom dynamics, and fulfill professional responsibilities effectively.

Conclusions

The study's findings the importance of patience as a professional attribute that positively influences various aspects of teaching performance. Supporting teachers in developing patience can contribute to their overall effectiveness, job satisfaction, and ability to promote positive educational outcomes for students.

Moreover, the study highlighted the importance of patience as a professional attribute that positively influences various aspects of teaching performance. Supporting teachers in developing patience can contribute to their overall effectiveness, job satisfaction, and ability to promote positive educational outcomes for students.

These safely judged that the responses of the teacher respondents on their degree of professional attributes in terms of time management have high significant relationships to their level of teaching performance in terms of planning and preparation, classroom environment, instruction, and professional responsibilities.

In summary, the quality of teacher education, continuous professional development, and the personal attributes of teachers are all essential components that contribute to teaching excellence and the overall quality of education in a nation. Teachers play a critical role in achieving high-quality education for all learners, and investing in teacher preparation is crucial for the future development of a nation. Teachers need continuous professional development and access to professional support throughout their careers to ensure they can effectively foster student learning and help students reach their full potential.

Recommendations

Based on the results and discussions presented, the following recommendations can be made for improving the professional attributes of teachers and their level of teaching performance:

Teachers should continue to focus on enhancing their adaptability skills to effectively navigate changes in curriculum or school policies. Professional development opportunities can help educators stay flexible and responsive to evolving educational requirements and shifts in the educational landscape.

Teachers should continue to prioritize providing adequate time and support for students who require additional assistance. Personalized support and individualized attention significantly contribute to student learning outcomes and academic success. Creating inclusive learning environments where all students can thrive is essential for fostering both academic and social-emotional development.

Continued Emphasis on Diverse Resources and Technologies: The high weighted mean and top rank for using a variety of resources and technologies indicate their perceived effectiveness in enhancing student learning. Teachers should continue to explore and integrate diverse tools and technologies into their teaching practices to cater to diverse learning styles and provide more interactive learning experiences.

Fostering Creativity and Expression of Ideas: While teachers strongly agree on the importance of encouraging creativity, the slightly lower weighted mean and rank suggest potential areas for further enhancement or exploration. Educators should actively seek ways to integrate creativity into their teaching practices, providing students with opportunities to think creatively and express their ideas.

The study's findings have significant implications for educational policy and practice. They emphasize the importance of fostering a supportive and collaborative educational environment where teachers are encouraged to develop their leadership skills, mentor their colleagues, and serve as positive role models for their students. By focusing on these key professional attributes, educators can create a more effective and enriching learning experience for all students.

Parent and Community Engagement: Engage parents and the community in supporting the development of these professional attributes. This could involve involving parents in teacher training and development programs, providing opportunities for community members to share their perspectives and experiences, and promoting a sense of shared responsibility for student success.

Overall, these recommendations aim to support teachers in developing their professional attributes and improving their level of teaching performance. By focusing on these competencies, teachers can better meet the needs of their students and create more effective and equitable learning environments.

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